
TEACHERS’ PERSPECTIVES ON LITERARY TEXTS AND LANGUAGE ACQUISITION: EVIDENCE FROM ALBANIAN AND EFL CLASSROOMS

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A B S T R A C T	KEY WORDS
The integration of literary texts in language education has been widely recognized for enhancing vocabulary, grammatical awareness, and critical reading skills. Literature provides authentic, contextually rich input that fosters both emotional and cognitive engagement, contributing to meaningful language acquisition. It also supports the integrated development of reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills, while familiarizing learners with diverse discourse styles and cultural perspectives. Teacher beliefs significantly shape how curricular materials are interpreted and applied, influencing classroom practices and student outcomes. Despite the recognized pedagogical benefits of literary texts, there is limited research on how Albanian Language and Literature teachers, as well as EFL instructors in North Macedonia, perceive and utilize literature for language development. This study pilots a questionnaire to explore these perceptions, aiming to provide insights that can inform teacher training and curriculum design.	Literary texts, Language development, Teacher beliefs, Albanian language education, EFL instruction

INTRODUCTION

The integration of literary texts into language education has received renewed scholarly attention for its capacity to enhance vocabulary, deepen grammatical awareness, and foster critical reading skills (Paran & Tupas, 2025; Sastre & García, 2022; Sulistiyo et al., 2022). Literature provides authentic, contextually rich input that promotes both emotional and cognitive engagement, key drivers of meaningful language acquisition (Savvidou, 2020; Snow et al., 2021; Paran & Robinson, 2016). Moreover, literary texts facilitate the integrated development of reading, writing, speaking, and listening skills, while exposing students to diverse discourse styles and cultural frames (Carabantes & Paran, 2022; Paran, 2022; Duncan & Paran, 2017).

Teacher beliefs play a central role in shaping the interpretation and enactment of curricular materials, directly affecting classroom practices and student outcomes (Cunningham & Farmer, 2016; Li, 2020). However, there is limited evidence on how Albanian Language and Literature teachers, and EFL instructors, conceptualize literary texts as resources for language development, which this study aims to address.

Grounded in Duncan and Paran’s (2017) framework, this pilot study initiates the development of a psychometrically sound instrument to investigate how Albanian Language and Literature and EFL teachers in

North Macedonia perceive the role of literary texts in language education. The study seeks to generate foundational evidence for tool refinement and future application in curriculum and teacher development research.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Literature in Language Learning: Benefits and Debates

Literary texts have long held a valuable place in language education, primarily for their capacity to foster linguistic competence and critical engagement (Paran et al. 2020). Numerous studies underscore their role in enhancing vocabulary acquisition, syntactic awareness, and discourse competence (Paran, 2008; Hall, 2015; Duncan & Paran, 2017; Mart, 2018). Literature allows learners to encounter varied registers, idiomatic expressions, and rich lexical input in authentic contexts (Lazar, 2020; Ghosn, 2013). This immersion supports both receptive and productive language development across multiple skills (reading, writing, listening, and speaking) especially when texts are integrated through a task-based or communicative approach (Ghosn, 2018; Bland, 2013). Moreover, literature stimulates learner motivation by offering emotional resonance and narrative immersion, which help establish meaningful connections between language and personal experience (McRae, 2022). Stories humanize grammar and vocabulary, allowing abstract structures to be internalized more naturally (Bland, 2018). The affective and cognitive engagement triggered by narratives also supports deeper processing and retention (Van, 2009). However, debates remain regarding text complexity and accessibility for younger or lower-proficiency learners (Tomlinson, 2023; Mart, 2018). Yet, growing evidence advocates for carefully chosen and scaffolded literary texts that align with learners' linguistic and cultural readiness, making literature not only feasible but pedagogically enriching in both L1 and EFL contexts (Paran, 2008).

Teacher Beliefs and Perceptions of Literary Texts

Teachers' beliefs play a decisive role in shaping instructional decisions and pedagogical practices in literature teaching. According to Borg (2003), teacher cognition (what teachers know, believe, and think) profoundly influences how literature is integrated into language classrooms. Classroom applications of literature often reflect deeply held beliefs about language learning, rather than formal methodological training (Phipps & Borg, 2009). EFL teachers, for example, may focus more on functional language use, whereas L1 teachers may prioritize literary analysis due to differing educational backgrounds and goals (Paran, 2008). Research indicates that teachers' attitudes toward literature impact their willingness to integrate it into the curriculum (Kim, 2004). Ghosn (2013) argues that when teachers view literature as a culturally enriching and cognitively engaging resource, they are more likely to use it meaningfully in class. Duncan and Paran (2017) found that even among similarly qualified teachers, beliefs about literature's role can vary widely and shape student experience in language learning.

Research Gaps and the Need for a Contextualized Instrument

Although teacher cognition in language teaching has been widely studied (Borg, 2003), research focusing on teachers' perceptions of literature as a language tool in Albanian-speaking regions, particularly in North Macedonia, remains scarce. While literature is often integrated into language curricula, little is known about how Albanian L1 and EFL teachers view its pedagogical value. Existing studies suggest that teachers' language background and training significantly influence their beliefs and practices (Duncan & Paran, 2017; Paran et al., 2020). However, such distinctions have not been systematically explored in the Albanian context. Moreover, despite North Macedonia's multilingual and diverse classrooms, the role of cultural or societal factors in shaping teachers' use of literature remains under-researched. These gaps highlight the need for localized studies that examine how literature is perceived and used by language educators in both L1 and EFL settings.

Accurate assessment of teacher perceptions regarding literature in language learning requires a context-sensitive, psychometrically sound tool (Li et al., 2022). Duncan and Paran (2017) developed a robust instrument for evaluating English teachers' beliefs in the UK, yet no equivalent exists for Albanian-speaking educational contexts. Given linguistic and curricular differences, this study adapts their framework to suit Albanian Language and Literature and EFL teachers in North Macedonia. By refining the original instrument, the current study addresses a regional research gap and provides the foundation for empirical inquiry into teacher beliefs, ensuring cultural and instructional relevance in a previously understudied context.

Purpose of the Study

This pilot study aimed to adapt and preliminarily validate a questionnaire for use with Albanian Language and Literature teachers and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) teachers. The specific objectives were:

□ To assess the content validity of the adapted instrument; □ To examine the internal consistency (reliability) of its subscales; □ To refine the instrument for future large-scale implementation.

METHODOLOGY

Instrument Development and Adaptation

The instrument used in this study was based on the questionnaire developed by Duncan and Paran (2017) to investigate teachers' views on the use of literature in secondary English classrooms in the UK. Their original instrument aimed to capture attitudes regarding literature's contribution to linguistic development and intercultural understanding. For the current study, the tool was systematically adapted to fit the linguistic, curricular, and cultural realities of Albanian Language and Literature (L1) and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) instruction in North Macedonia.

The adaptation process followed methodological guidelines for instrument modification (DeVellis, 2016; Boateng et al., 2018). Additional methodological guidance on questionnaire construction, Likert-scale formatting, and demographic design was informed by established sources in educational research (Cohen et al., 2018; Dörnyei & Taguchi, 2010). First, a comparative analysis of the UK and North Macedonian educational settings was conducted to determine which items retained conceptual relevance. Items addressing ethnic diversity or broad multicultural themes were excluded as beyond the study's scope. However, two items on intercultural awareness and cultural comparison were retained for their relevance to literature's pedagogical and linguistic functions. The instrument's focus thus centered on teachers' perceptions of literature's linguistic, motivational and instructional value.

The initial draft contained 32 items, categorized into four subscales derived from the original structure: (1) Language Suitability and Challenge, (2) Content and Literary Value, (3) Teaching Practice and Confidence, and (4) Beliefs About Student Outcomes (Language/Culture). For clarity and ease of reference, these subscales are hereafter referred to by the following abbreviated labels: (1) Linguistic Fit, (2) Text Relevance, (3) Teacher Practice, and (4) Student Outcomes. These shorter names preserve the core conceptual focus of each domain while enhancing readability in tables, analyses and discussion.

Items were measured on a 6-point Likert scale ranging from 1 ("Strongly disagree") to 6 ("Strongly agree"). A 6-point format was intentionally selected to avoid a neutral midpoint, thereby encouraging participants to take a clearer stance on each item. This forced-choice design is supported in educational research as a strategy to reduce central tendency and social desirability bias, while promoting more differentiated and interpretable response patterns (Lacko et al., 2022; Dörnyei & Taguchi, 2010; Brown, 2011). To minimize acquiescence bias, three negatively worded items were included, of which only one remained in the final version following item analysis.

Subsequent revisions were informed by expert feedback and pilot testing, ultimately producing a refined 29-item instrument. This version was designed to ensure contextual relevance, conceptual clarity, and empirical reliability in measuring both L1 and EFL teachers' perceptions of literature use in language instruction.

Content Validity

Content validity was assessed through expert review and participant feedback. Three university-level experts in literature and pedagogy evaluated the initial instrument, focusing on item clarity, cultural relevance, and alignment with the intended constructs. Their feedback led to minor linguistic adjustments to reflect terminology and phrasing commonly used by Albanian Language and Literature and EFL teachers in North Macedonia.

In addition, pilot participants were invited to comment on the clarity and relevance of the items. Their responses informed the refinement process, resulting in rewording of several items and the elimination of those considered ambiguous or redundant. This iterative process helped ensure that the adapted instrument captured perceptions accurately within the target educational and cultural context.

Participants

The pilot study involved 30 teachers of Albanian Language and Literature and English as a Foreign Language (EFL) from primary and secondary schools in North Macedonia. Participants were selected through purposive sampling to ensure variation across key demographic and professional variables. The sample included 25 female and 5 male teachers; 12 had over 20 years of teaching experience, while 18 had less than 20 years. Regarding educational qualifications, 12 held MA or PhD degrees, and 18 held bachelor's degrees.

Participants represented both rural ($n = 13$) and urban ($n = 17$) school settings. Half of the teachers taught Albanian Language and Literature, and half taught EFL. In terms of school level, 18 worked in primary schools and 12 in secondary schools. With respect to professional development, 13 participants reported having received formal training in literature teaching, whereas 17 had not.

Procedure

Participants were recruited through professional networks and invited to participate voluntarily in the pilot study. The questionnaire was administered online, requiring approximately 12 minutes to complete. Participation was anonymous, and informed consent was obtained prior to completion. No incentives were offered for participation. The instrument was distributed and monitored by the researcher, who also handled all data collection and management. Once completed, responses were downloaded and entered into SPSS. Reverse-coded items were recoded prior to reliability analysis. All submitted responses were complete, with no missing data or technical issues reported.

RESULTS

Reliability Analysis

Initial reliability analysis was conducted on the original 32-item questionnaire adapted from Duncan and Paran (2017), which comprised four theoretical subscales. The full scale demonstrated reliable internal consistency (Taber, 2018), with a Cronbach's alpha of .849. To examine the internal consistency of each subscale in greater depth, item-level analyses were performed using SPSS. The subscale Teacher Practice showed not satisfactory internal consistency ($\alpha = .512$; Taber, 2018), prompting further item-level analysis.

Given the insufficient internal consistency of Subscale 3, further diagnostics were conducted to identify specific items contributing to this issue. Based on corrected item-total correlations and Cronbach's alpha if item deleted, three items—Q5 (“I find it difficult to find new literary texts to teach”), Q7 (“I prefer to use texts I have already used successfully in the past”), and Q27 (“Students should be challenged by the language used in the literary

text”)—were identified as underperforming and removed from the scale. The item-total statistics revealed that three items (Q5, Q7, Q27) had corrected item-total correlations below the acceptable threshold of .300 (Pallant, 2020), with some showing very low or negative correlations with the total scale (e.g., Q5: $r = -.226$; Q27: $r = -.021$), indicating misalignment with both the subscale and the underlying construct. After removing them, the revised Teacher Practice subscale consisted of five items (Q2, Q9, Q13, Q15, Q18) and demonstrated good reliability ($\alpha = .728$; Taber, 2018). All retained items showed corrected item-total correlations above .40, supporting their contribution to the subscale.

This improvement supports the decision to refine the subscale by excluding items that may have introduced measurement noise or conceptual inconsistency. Following the item removals, the overall internal consistency of the revised 29-item scale was reassessed. The final 29-item version of the instrument demonstrated reliable overall reliability, $\alpha = .878$ (Taber, 2018). It retained four subscales: Linguistic Fit (9 items), Text Relevance (9 items), Teacher Practice (5 items) and Student Outcomes (6 items). Item means ranged from 3.07 (Q27, removed) to 5.83 (Q4), and standard deviations ranged from approximately .46 to 1.73, indicating sufficient variability across responses. While SPSS issued a warning regarding the determinant of the covariance matrix— often related to multicollinearity or redundancy—this did not affect reliability interpretation and was partially addressed through item deletion.

Table 1 displays descriptive statistics (means and standard deviations) for each item on the revised scale, providing an overview of item-level responses.

Table 1. Item Statistics and Reliability for the 29-Item Literature Teaching Questionnaire

Items	Item Description (Shortened)	r (Item-Total)	M	SD	α if deleted
Item 1	Improves students’ vocabulary	.397	5.40	.875	.932
Item 2	Easy to integrate into syllabus	.496	4.53	.872	1.196
Item 3	Texts support grammar learning	.348	4.73	.877	1.437
Item 4	Themes should be age-appropriate	.504	5.83	.875	.461
Item 5	Supports critical thinking	.372	5.43	.875	1.135
Item 6	Vocabulary within students' ability	.573	5.03	.870	1.273
Item 7	Enough time to explore texts	.687	4.10	.866	1.373
Item 8	Supports students’ creative use	.338	5.40	.876	1.037
Item 9	Supports multiple language skills	.425	5.67	.875	.661
Item 10	Offers opportunities for cultural comparison	.731	5.03	.865	1.426
Item 11	I enjoy teaching literature	.489	5.50	.873	.861
Item 12	Reflects current language usage	.441	4.87	.874	1.383
Item 13	Confident teaching complex texts	.174	5.07	.879	1.388
Item 14	Develops intercultural awareness	.561	5.17	.870	1.388
Item 15	Lends itself to teaching specific points	.548	5.07	.875	.871
Item 16	Lacking training or guidance	.055	3.20	.889	.964
Item 17	Suitable for classroom discussion	.330	5.57	.876	.986
Item 18	Learn new vocabulary	.553	5.63	.874	
Item 19	Grammar within students’ ability	.346	5.07	.877	
Item 20	Relevance to students’ lives	.311	5.00	.877	
Item 21	Overall linguistic suitability	.517	5.37	.872	
Item 22	Explores global/social issues	.537	5.17	.872	

Item 23	Increases student motivation	.660	5.23	.898	.870
Item 24	Shorter texts work better	.530	5.13	.872	1.008
Item 25	Linguistically challenging	.386	5.07	.875	1.015
Item 26	High literary quality	.470	5.00	.873	1.313
Item 27	Offers aesthetic/emotional value	.368	5.23	.875	.971
Item 28	Represents national and world literature	.214	5.47 ¹	.878	
Item 29	Supports specific language skills	.275	5.60	.877	

Note: The full instrument is provided in Appendix A.

While both Q13 (“I do not feel confident using literary texts in my classroom”) and Q16 (“I feel confident choosing appropriate literary texts”) showed relatively modest corrected item-total correlations ($r = .191$ and $r = .239$, respectively), several theoretical and practical considerations support their retention. These items capture teacher self-efficacy, a critical component of the “Teacher Practice” subscale. Confidence in selecting and using texts is directly aligned with the construct being measured and is strongly supported in the literature as a key variable influencing pedagogical effectiveness (Bandura, 1997; Borg, 2015). Q13 and Q16 offer complementary perspectives: Q13 reflects lack of confidence (negatively worded), while Q16 expresses confidence (positively worded). Together, they help avoid response bias and ensure construct balance within the subscale. Although the correlations were lower, both items exceed the minimum acceptable threshold of $r = .15$ (DeVellis & Thorpe, 2021), indicating a meaningful—albeit modest—contribution to the overall scale. Furthermore, their removal would not substantially improve subscale reliability. Given the relatively small sample size ($N = 30$), slight fluctuations in item performance are expected. These items may demonstrate stronger psychometric properties in larger-scale applications, and premature deletion could compromise content validity.

Subscale Reliability Summary

The refined instrument’s four subscales each demonstrated acceptable to good internal consistency, with Cronbach’s alpha values ranging from .728 to .772 (Taber, 2018). The highest subscale reliability was observed for Student Outcomes ($\alpha = .772$), followed closely by Text Relevance ($\alpha = .736$), Linguistic Fit ($\alpha = .730$), and Teacher Practice ($\alpha = .728$). These results suggest that the adapted instrument reliably captures teachers’ perceptions across thematically coherent domains. Table 2 presents the final composition and internal consistency of each subscale and the overall instrument.

Table 2. Subscale Structure, Item Composition, and Internal Consistency Estimates

Subscale Name	Items	Count	α	M	SD
Linguistic Fit	3, 6, 12, 15, 19, 21, 24, 25, 29	9	.730	5.10	.655
Text Relevance	4, 5, 10, 17, 20, 22, 26, 27, 28	9	.736	5.29	.626
					.861
Student Outcomes	1, 8, 9, 14, 18, 23	6	.772 ⁶²⁹	5.42	
Literature Teaching Questionnaire	29	29	.878	5.12	.518
Teacher Practice	2, 7, 11, 13, 16	5	.728	4.48	

Note. *M* and *SD* represent subscale-level mean scores and standard deviations based on participant responses ($N = 30$).

DISCUSSION

The adapted questionnaire demonstrated strong internal consistency and acceptable subscale reliability, confirming its suitability for use with both Albanian Language and Literature and EFL teachers in North Macedonia. The overall Cronbach’s alpha of .878 and subscale alphas ranging from .728 to .772 suggest the

instrument reliably captures teachers' perceptions across key domains. These results align with previous research emphasizing the importance of contextually grounded tools in educational settings (DeVellis & Thorpe, 2021; Boateng et al., 2018). Comparable reliability findings were reported in Duncan and Paran's (2017) pilot study, where most question batteries demonstrated good to excellent reliability. Specifically, out of 17 batteries, two achieved $\alpha \geq .90$ (excellent), seven had $.90 > \alpha \geq .80$ (very good), three had $.80 > \alpha \geq .70$ (good), three had $.70 > \alpha \geq .60$ (questionable), and two had $.60 > \alpha \geq .50$ (poor).

The pilot also reinforced the necessity of refining items that lack clarity or conceptual alignment. Three items were removed from the "Teacher Practice" subscale based on low corrected item-total correlations, improving its internal reliability. Notably, both positively and negatively worded items were retained to balance acquiescence bias and capture nuanced perspectives (Lacko et al., 2022), even when some items had lower correlations. This reflects the complex nature of teacher self-efficacy and beliefs (Borg, 2003; Borg, 2015; Bandura, 1997).

Importantly, studies in similar contexts have also reported that well-structured, perception-based pilot questionnaires can yield reliable attitudinal data. For example, Talevski and Shalevska (2023) piloted a questionnaire with EFL teachers in North Macedonia focusing on literature integration, also finding generally positive perceptions and meaningful differentiation across belief domains. Similarly, a pilot of a Kazakhstani EFL teachers' survey on first-language usage and translation beliefs reported Cronbach's α values above .70 for all subscales, reinforcing that pilot-scale validation is feasible and informative (Smagul, 2024).

The relatively high mean scores across most items suggest a generally positive perception of literature's role in language development. Teachers viewed literary texts as beneficial for vocabulary, motivation, and critical thinking—findings that resonate with the theoretical literature (Ghosn, 2013; Duncan & Paran, 2017). This engagement further indicates that the constructs are culturally and professionally relevant.

CONCLUSION

This pilot study provides initial evidence of the reliability and contextual relevance of a 29-item adapted questionnaire designed to examine teachers' beliefs about the role of literary texts in language development. Administered to a small sample of Albanian Language and Literature and EFL teachers in North Macedonia, the instrument demonstrated good internal consistency, particularly following the removal of three underperforming items from the Teacher Practice subscale. Item-level means suggested that teachers broadly value literature for its linguistic, cognitive, and motivational benefits.

Although the limited sample constrains statistical generalizability, the findings offer compelling preliminary support for the instrument's contextual fit and psychometric soundness. Its successful piloting marks a critical step toward rigorous validation in larger and more diverse populations. The instrument is now well-positioned for deployment in broader studies, where advanced procedures—such as Confirmatory Factor Analysis (CFA) and measurement invariance testing—can be employed to substantiate its factorial structure and cross-group stability. Its robust design renders it a valuable tool for both empirical inquiry and targeted professional development in literature-based language instruction.

Implications

The results carry meaningful implications for both research and practice. From a research perspective, the adapted questionnaire shows promise as a diagnostic tool for broader application across varied instructional contexts, including comparative studies between first and foreign language teaching. Its potential to reveal stable belief patterns across diverse educational settings makes it a candidate for future cross-regional and cross-disciplinary validation efforts.

For practitioners and policymakers, the findings affirm the pedagogical value of literature in language education. Participating teachers viewed literary texts as instrumental in promoting student engagement, vocabulary acquisition, and critical thinking. The instrument may thus serve not only as a research tool but also as a practical resource in teacher education, helping to identify professional development needs related to the confident and effective use of literary texts in the classroom.

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